

DISTRIBUTION OF INDICATOR-SAPROBIC ALGAE SPECIES OF THE “UZUNBULAK” SEWAGE TREATMENT PLANT AND THEIR ECOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract: This article examines the development and distribution of indicator saprobic algae in the systems of the Uzunbulak wastewater treatment plant and their importance in the purification of the Zarafshan River water.

Keywords: Zarafshan River, Uzunbulak water treatment plant, algoflora, algae, indicator saprobic species, plankton, benthos.

Introduction. According to the Central Asian Journal of Geographical Research (No. 3-4. 2023), rivers and canals flowing on the territory of the republic within the boundaries of large industrial centers, irrigation systems of rural farms, and densely populated cities are exposed to anthropogenic influences, as a result of which their waters are polluted.

One of the important areas of monitoring the natural aquatic environment is the use of indicators. Saprobic indicator algae help predict the presence of water pollution by infectious microorganisms, which results in the spread of diseases among the population [1-10].

Analysis of the literature on the topic. In the work of N.V. Kondratyeva (2000), the views that became the property of the international community in 2001 (Kondratyeva, 2001) on various aspects of classification and analysis of diversity in algae, which absorb all the problems that currently exist in this area of science, are considered in detail [4], [5], [6], [7], [8].

In an alternative model proposed by V.A. Krasilov (1997), high diversity is a consequence (rather than a cause) of the sustainable development of ecosystems in relatively stable conditions. According to this model, diversity serves as an indicator of the efficiency of using energy resources, which increases both during biological evolution and in the process of ecological succession, briefly repeating the latter. The greater the efficiency, the smaller the number sufficient for sustainable reproduction of the population. Due to the increase in efficiency, the population density decreases to a certain limit, which is controlled by the stability of conditions: with frequent destructive impacts,

the population needs a reserve number, the reduction of which creates the danger of sudden extinction. Maintaining a reserve population slows down the growth of diversity, which stops at a relatively low level. One of the predictions of this model is that the reduction of diversity under stress occurs by delaying biological succession in early or intermediate stages. The study of the dynamics of diversity in ecosystems exposed to anthropogenic impact opens up the possibility of verifying these theoretical postulates. In recent years, many practical works have been carried out in this direction in our republic and other territories [1-10].

Materials and methods. The algoflora of the Zarafshan River was formed as a result of the complex influence of environmental factors. The river is divided into 3 parts, differing in such environmental factors as the chemical composition of water, water temperature, transparency, flow velocity, pH, etc.

The exact cause of the change in the color of the water can only be determined in the laboratory. But by the color and intensity of staining, even a layman can make a preliminary analysis and find out what foreign substances are present in the water from his plumbing, borehole, or well.

Determining the pH value of water is of great importance in assessing the quality of natural waters, and in assessing the corrosivity of water in drinking and industrial water supply systems. This indicator is also important in the treatment of drinking water, water treatment for industrial installations, and the disposal of household and factory wastewater.

The assessment of the state of reservoirs involves an extensive set of studies and observations. The methods used in algology are divided into hydrochemical, biological, and microbiological. Biological phenomena and processes occurring in the aquatic ecosystem are studied using biological research methods. Physico-chemical methods allow us to obtain information about the abiotic inanimate part of the ecosystem, and the results of numerous microbiological methods characterize the sanitary and hygienic condition of reservoirs [6], [7], [8], [9], [10].

Analysis and results. During the year, green (*Chlorophyta*) algae dominated in biological ponds, blue-green (*Cyanophyta*) in second place, and eugenic (*Euglenophyta*) in third (*Bacillariophyta*) [1], [3].

25 indicator species and forms of algae were found in the Zarafshan River above the discharge, among which Bacillariophyta (37.2%) and α -meso- and o-saprobies (14% each) predominate in terms of the number of species and forms. Species typical of reservoirs with a lower degree of pollution (from β -

mesosaprobites to x-saprobites) were often found here, *Hydrurus foetidus*, *Meridion circulare*, *Diatoma hiemale*, and *D.hiemalevar.mesodon*, *Navicula cryptocephala* and others typical of pure oligotrophic reservoirs were most often found here, which indicates the purity of the water in this section of the river. A total of 46, or 32.2%, indicator species and forms of algae were found at this site. Among them, the number of species is dominated by β -mesosaprobites (46.2%) and α -mesosaprobites (16.8%). These algae are mainly *Merismopedia glauca*, *Oscillatoria brevis*, *O. limosa*, *O. sancta*, *Gleothoececon fluens*, *Surirella ovate*, *Scenedesmus acuminatus*, *S. bijugatus* and others. As a result of the analysis, it is shown that the composition of indicator forms of algae according to the stages of purification, starting from primary sedimentation tanks and ending with biological ponds, gradually decreases from indicators of high to indicators of low degrees of pollution. We found 173 species in the reservoirs of the Jizzakh sewage treatment plant system and in the studied points of the Zarafshan River. Of the 173 algae species, 59 (34.1%) belong to planktonic, 13 to blue-green, 9 to euglenic, 3 to dinophytic, 15 to diatom, 3 to yellow-green, and 16 to green algae. in p. (Table 1).

Table 1.

Ecological characteristics of algoflora by the nature of their habitat in water

№	Algae Department	planktonic		planktonic-benthic		benthic		Total	
		max.	%	max.	%	max.	%	max.	%
1	<i>Cyanophyta</i>	13	7,5	24	14	10	6	47	27,1
2	<i>Chrysophyta</i>	3	1,7	1	0,5	1	0,5	5	2,8
3	<i>Bacillariophyta</i>	15	8,6	15	8,6	7	4	37	21,3
4	<i>Xantophyta</i>	-	-	2	1,1	-	-	2	1,2
5	<i>Dinophyta</i>	3	1,7	1	0,5	-	-	4	2,4
6	<i>Euglenophyta</i>	9	5,3	2	1,2	-	-	11	6,4
7	<i>Chlorophyta</i>	16	9,3	42	24,3	5,1	5,1	67	38,7
	Total	59	34,1	87	50,2	15,6	15,6	173	100,0

Table 2.

Ecological characteristics of algoflora about water salinity

№	Algae department	freshwater		freshwater-brackish-water		brackish water		Total	
		max.	%	max.	%	max.	%	max.	%

1	<i>Cyanophyta</i>	13	7,5	24	14	10	6	47	27,1
2	<i>Chrysophyta</i>	3	1,7	1	0,5	1	0,5	5	2,8
3	<i>Bacillariophyta</i>	15	8,6	15	8,6	7	4	37	21,3
4	<i>Xantophyta</i>	-	-	2	1,1	-	-	2	1,2
5	<i>Dinophyta</i>	3	1,7	1	0,5	-	-	4	2,4
6	<i>Euglenophyta</i>	9	5,3	2	1,2	-	-	11	6,4
7	<i>Chlorophyta</i>	16	9,3	42	24,3	5,1	5,1	67	38,7
	Total	59	34, 1	87	50,2	15,6	15,6	173	100, 0

Zarafshan, due to the shallow water, high flow velocity, and porosity, planktonic forms of algae are absent [2], [9]. Benthic forms such as *Achnanthes lanceolata*, and *Nitzschia linearis* are found in plankton samples. *Dinobryon divergens*, *Euglena acus*, *Phacus acuminatus*, etc. are found in plankton. Typical benthic algae of 27 species (15.6%) include *Gloeocapsa compacta*, *Ulotrix zonata*, *Synedra gouldardii*, and others. Planktonic-benthic forms are very common in the surveyed reservoirs (87 taxa – 50.2%).

97 taxa (74.06%) belong to freshwater algae. Among them are *Phormidium foveolarum*, *Achnanthes minutissima*, *A. lanceolata*, *Navicula cryptocephala*, etc. There are 55 freshwater-brackish-water species and intraspecific taxa (22.32%). Of these, *Merismopedia glauca*, *M. elegans*, *Microcystis aeruginosa*, *Oscillatoria brevis*, *O. amoena*, *O. sancta* and others should be noted.

Typically, there are few brackish algae compared to freshwater and brackish algae - 20 species (3.62%). These include *Microcystis pulvereae*, *Oscillatoria brevis*, *O. amoena*, *O. sancta*, etc. (Table.2) [1], [2], [3].

Conclusions. Interacting in the process of evolution, the living and inorganic elements of the aquatic ecosystem mutually determine their performance. Biological diversity, as a list of species and as an indicator of the complexity of organizing communities of organisms, reflects changes in environmental indicators, in turn, affecting their values. Interdependent indicators of the environment and communities of organisms characterize a certain state of the ecosystem that exists within certain boundaries of change. Thus, the development and distribution of organisms in systems are determined primarily by the ecological environment, such as temperature, light, mineral and organic substances dissolved in water, gas regime, pH, fluctuations in the water level and the speed of its rotation.

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